

FEED AND SUBREFLECTOR ALIGNMENT IN A GREGORIAN COMPACT RANGE

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Abstract

Efforts to reduce edge taper, cross polarization errors, and feed spillover have resulted in the use of a dual reflector system for compact range applications. Two of the most popular configurations are the Cassegrain and Gregorian systems. NASA Langley Research Center has built a dual-chamber Gregorian compact Experimental Test Range (ETR) currently in use with a 16-ft. blended rolled-edge main reflector. The dual-chamber concept improves the overall performance of the compact range by attenuating the feed spillover radiation in addition to reducing the edge taper problem and cross polarization errors. The Gregorian system adds complexity to compact ranges already sensitive to alignment criteria. This paper addresses the task of creating a procedure for aligning and focusing a subreflector system.

Range Setup

The measure of performance of a compact range is the amplitude and phase deviation within the quiet zone volume. The amplitude should be uniform everywhere in the volume and the phase should be uniform on a plane perpendicular to the direction of propagation. For our range alignment, a single axis prober was placed either vertically or horizontally in the quiet zone, parallel to the plane of propagation, and measured the magnitude and phase as a function of position in the quiet zone. Alignment of a simple focus-fed compact range requires the adjustment of the feed in five axes and the prober in two axes. The large main reflector remained fixed in ETR and was used as the reference. Adding a subreflector adds another 5 degrees of freedom to the 7 axes in a focus-fed range. The subreflector alignment was coupled to the feed alignment such that an error in feed placement could be partially corrected with a subreflector adjustment. A new alignment procedure was used due to this interdependence problem.

The microwave 'measuring stick' used in aligning a range is the phase variation measured in the quiet zone. The $\exp(-jkz)$ phase dependence in the direction of propagation translates into decreasing phase value as a function of path length, and this was used to determine the direction in which to adjust the feed or subreflector. A frequency of 10 GHz was used throughout the alignment so that fine adjustments of 1/32 inch produced workable phase changes of about 5-10. The prober was used in both horizontal (x axis) and vertical (y axis) scans and was placed about 20 feet down range (about the center of the quiet zone) from the main reflector. An adjustment of the prober mount was made so that it was physically aligned with the main reflector, fixing the prober's alignment.

Main Reflector Focal Point Location

A feed horn was located in the approximate focal point location of our main reflector and moved on its 3 translational degrees of freedom until the optimal focal point location was determined. The 3 rotational degrees of freedom about the x, y, and z axes need not be precisely aligned though the feed should be placed closely to its designed position. The x and y rotation controls the amplitude taper in the y and x directions respectively, while the z rotation controls the polarization alignment. These adjustments were made to the subreflector/feed system. In general, the phase variation on the probing scans contained a concave/convex component (fig. 3 and 4) and a linear slope component (fig. 1). Higher order effects (fig. 2) were also seen but they were primarily due to inappropriate prober placement in the quiet zone and to a lesser extent chamber and small reflector surface distortions. The linear component visible on a horizontal scan can be removed simply by adjusting the focus-fed horn in the x direction keeping in mind that the feed must be moved in the direction of the more negative phase values.

The removal of the concave/convex component requires the adjustment of the feed in the y' and z' directions. To properly accomplish this, information from both horizontal and vertical scans are necessary. With the linear component of

the horizontal scan removed, the phase should look something like figure 3 or figure 4. A convex shape can be removed by moving the feed along the +z' axis or some combination of +z and -y as adjustment allows. This increases the center to edge of the reflector distance ratio and flattens the phase. A concave shape requires adjustment in the opposite sense (i.e., -z' or, -z and +y). When the phase is uniform in the horizontal scan, the feed must be somewhere along the y' axis, and this is where it pays off to have an axis adjustment in the primed system instead of the unprimed coordinate system as we did.

The next step is to move the prober to the vertical scan direction and determine whether the phase is convex or concave. In general, there is a large linear component imposed on this curve and, as we shall see, the two components are removed together. Feed departure from the focus along the y' axis produces a linear phase taper, with increasing phase in the direction of deviation. If the main reflector were a plane, only the linear component would be present, but the curvature produces a convex/concave component in addition. A convex shape requires adjustment in the -y' direction, and a concave shape requires adjustment in the +y' direction. Proper adjustment at this point yielded a flat phase in both horizontal and vertical probing directions which should be verified by examining the horizontal scan again. In actuality some iteration was necessary. At this point, the range was focused in the prime focal-fed configuration, and the point was marked in space with a stylus referenced to the floor.

Feed-Subreflector Alignment

Alignment of the feed-subreflector system independent of the main reflector was done next. After a coarse yard stick alignment of the feed, which was probably accurate to 1/4 inch, backscatter measurements were made to locate the two foci of the Gregorian subreflector. A 2-inch sphere was hung by a thread (fig. 6) in the approximate location of the focal point in the aperture and was moved to maximize the returned power to the feed. Keeping the sphere in a constant location, the feed was then moved to increase the return further. This procedure was iterated until the backscattered power could not be increased. A 1-inch sphere was then used and forward scattering or transmission loss measurements were made to validate the correct locations of the feed and aperture focal point. Transmission loss measurements seemed to be more sensitive than the return loss measurements.

The stylus was placed in its correct position over the subreflector to locate the focal point of the main reflector. The objective here was to get the location of the 1-inch sphere as close as possible to the stylus tip to minimize the subreflector

adjustment. Since the subreflector was much larger than feeds used in compact range applications; care, advanced planning, and some tips given here can save time in subreflector alignment. First, the subreflector translational adjustments were done in the same way as the feed adjustment in the prime focal-fed configuration, with the exception of the cross range alignment. Second, the 3 rotational degrees of freedom were reduced to 1 before the phase alignment procedure began. Rotational freedom about the z axis was eliminated by physical alignment with the main reflector and polarization alignment from the horizontal probe scan. The x axis was adjusted in the same way the feed tilt in a focal-fed range was adjusted. Instead of tilting the subreflector, the feed was tilted to minimize edge taper in the quiet zone amplitude. With the x and z axes fixed, rotation about the y axis fixed the cross range alignment, eliminating the need for a cross range translational adjustment. The goal here was to get the feed's phase center and the two focal points (main and subreflector) aligned. After physically aligning the feed to the main reflector with a plumb bob, the horizontal probe data were used to remove the linear component based on subreflector rotation about the feed's phase center.

In summary, the following sequence was realized:

- 1) Alignment of the prober with the main reflector
- 2) Prime focus-fed adjustment for main reflector focal point location
- 3) Coarse feed-subreflector alignment
- 4) Backward and forward scattering measurements with a 1-inch sphere at the subreflector focus to finely tune the feed location
- 5) Coarse subreflector-main reflector alignment based on results from 2) & 4)
- 6) Cross range alignment
- 7) System focusing
- 8) An optional main reflector illumination adjustment

In actual practice, there was a certain degree of iteration involved with the above steps yielding an optimal range alignment.

The procedures described above ensure a planar wave will be present in the quiet zone at the prober location. In order to make the amplitude uniform, feed tilt and stray scattering must be reduced. While feed tilt can minimize the edge taper problem, the problems of stray scattering from the reflector edges, coupling aperture for the subreflector, and various surfaces in the anechoic chamber are more difficult to solve.

Figure 1.-Linear component.

Figure 2.-Higher order component.

Figure 3.-Convex component.

Figure 4.-Concave component.

Figure 5

Figure 6